

**Digital
Water
.City**

D 6.2

Set-up of DWC website

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Related Work Package:	WP6
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Duration of the project:	42 months
Website:	www.digital-water.city
Abstract	

Dissemination level of the document

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU	Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the European Commission Services)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the European Commission Services)

Versioning and Contribution History

Version	Date	Modified by	Modification reasons
v.02			
v.03			
v.04			
v.05			

1. Set-up of the website

1.1. Some elements from the visual identity

Arctik has already designed the visual identity and brand for digital-water.city (Deliverable 6.1), respecting the EC guidelines for research projects. This visual identity is central for the set-up of the website.

The design of the logo tells the story of the project at a glance : buildings represent the urban side of the project and waves the water component. The different blue colors are also associated with water. Furthermore, the name of the project and the URL of the website (without dash) are also written next to the logo for an immediate understanding.

Logotype on white background

Figure 1 - Logotype on white background

As part of the visual identity, some specific icons were designed: they represent the core objectives – health protection, performance and return on investment, public involvement – as well as some filters to select digital solutions on the website.

Figure 2 - Icons

A selection of 4 pictures has also been made and will be used on the website.

Pictures - water

Figure 3 – Pictures

1.2. Set-up of the temporary website

Before launching the full website for DWC, the consortium has decided to put online a **temporary one**. The official URL www.digital-water.city that corresponds to the full name of the project has been bought.

This temporary website does present the overall project at glance. Therefore, we have decided to go for simple scroll-down webpage gathering all necessary information. As soon as the user lands on the homepage, the logo and the slogan of DWC appear with a short video clip representing water waves in the background.

Snapshot 1 – Welcome page of the temporary website digital-water.city

When the user scrolls down, he then gets through the following steps:

Snapshot 1 - Temporary website / 1st step : What is at stake?

BERLIN – MILAN – COPENHAGEN – PARIS – SOFIA

30 000 000

inhabitants

Our solution

To face current and future challenges, digital technologies are acknowledged as key enabler to improve water management. The main goal of Digital Water City is to boost with these technologies the integrated management of waters systems in five major European urban and peri-urban areas – Berlin, Milan, Copenhagen, Paris and Sofia – representing 30 million inhabitants

-
-
-
-
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Snapshot 2 - Temporary website / 2nd step : Our solution

More exactly

Digital Water City will develop and demonstrate 18 advanced digital solutions to address current and future water-related challenges. Areas of application of DWC digital solutions range from groundwater management, sewer maintenance and operation, wastewater treatment and reuse to urban bathing water management.

18

advanced digital solution

-
-
-
-
-

Snapshot 3 - Temporary website / 3rd step – More exactly

Snapshot 4 - Temporary website / 4th step – Next step: Twitter

1.3. Set-up of the full website

1.3.1. Description

Arctik is currently working to deliver a full website, which will be available online by the end of October (2019) at the same URL: www.digital-water.city.

The website has been designed respecting the project's **visual identity** (see previous section) and by making use of attractive visuals to enhance the visual appeal of the website.

It will include a scroll-down **landing page** gathering all necessary information at a glance. After clicking on “Dive into Digital Water City”, the user will get some answers to questions like “What?”, “Why?” and “Where?” presenting the overall project. An overview of some of the digital solutions and 5 demonstration cities, as well as the latest news, will appear and give a more dynamic content to this landing page.

Focus will be also put on fresh and appealing webpages for each of the **15 technologies** and **5 demo sites** to ensure a strong and direct visibility of the digital solutions. Some additional sections will be created like **“Digital integration”**, **“Resources”** and **“Get in touch”**.

As the project unfolds and more information about the 15 digital solutions becomes available, we plan to update the website in order to further emphasize them.

An internal communication and exchange platform is already set up on www.cloud.digital-water.city.

1.3.2. Menu

In a nutshell, the menu is the following one:

- 1) About digital-water.city
 - a. At a glance
 - b. Background and objectives
 - c. Meet the team
- 2) Digital cities
 - a. Berlin
 - b. Copenhagen
 - c. Milan
 - d. Paris
 - e. Sofia
- 3) Digital integration
- 4) Digital solutions
- 5) Resources
- 6) Newsroom
- 7) Get in touch

1.3.1. Snapshots

The following snapshots give a complete view of the different sections of the full website:

Snapshot 1 - Full website / Homepage

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<p>COORDINATION</p> <p>Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin gGmbH (KWB) 24 partners from 10 European countries 5 cities: Berlin, Copenhagen, Milan, Paris, Sofia</p>									
Total volume	5.9 Mio. €								
Total Grant	5.0 Mio. €								
Grant KWB	724,500 €								

Snapshot I - Full website / About digital-water.city - At a glance

ABOUT

European cities face major challenges to achieve the desired level of sustainability in the management of urban water systems. Digital technologies such as mobile devices, real-time sensors, machine learning, artificial intelligence and cloud solutions have the potential to improve the management of water infrastructures significantly. In addition, they can improve the quality of services provided to citizens as well as the level of awareness and collaboration between utilities, authorities and citizens.

 DWC's main goal is to boost the integrated management of waters systems in five major European cities – Berlin, Milan, Copenhagen, Paris and Sofia – by leveraging the potential of data and smart digital technologies.

The solutions are developed in close collaboration between municipalities, utilities, research institutes and innovation players from both digital and physical spheres. DWC integrates the development of digital solutions in a dedicated guiding protocol to cover the existing gaps regarding governance, interoperability and cybersecurity.

In **Berlin**, several innovations will reduce the environmental impacts of the sewer network focusing on illicit connections, combined sewer overflows and optimize the maintenance and planning of water wells. An Augmented Reality application visualize the groundwater flows for the public and highlight the relevance of drinking water resource as hidden part of the water cycle.

In **Paris**, DWC aims at improving the bathing water quality in the river Seine for the Olympic games of 2024 using innovative sensors for bacterial measurements in the river and machine learning to forecast the contamination risk at the official bathing places.

Follow us on **twitter**

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Digital-water.city has received funding from the European Union's H2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 820954

Arctik Communication for sustainability

Snapshot 2 - Full website / About digital-water.city – Background and objectives

MEET THE TEAM

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<p>WebTech</p>			
<p>BRAND NAME TAGLINE</p>			
<p>COMPANYNAME</p>			

Snapshot 3 - Full website / About digital-water.city - Meet the team

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Snapshot 4 - Full website / Digital cities

BERLIN

OBJECTIVES

CHALLENGES

ACTIVITIES

What's news?

BERLIN PROTECT HIS WATER

LOREM IPSUM FOR THIS NEW TITLE

The digital solutions of Berlin

digital solutions by M. Assaf and M. Assaf for digital solutions to address current and future water-related challenges

The first digital solution

LEARN MORE ABOUT THIS SOLUTION

CONTACT & INFORMATIONS

Nathalie Simon
nathalie.simon@digital-water.city

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Snapshot 5 - Full website / Digital cities - Berlin

Snapshot 6 - Full website / Digital solutions

Snapshot 7 - Full website / Example of a digital solution

[Home](#)
[About](#)
[Twitter](#)

[About Digital-water city](#)
[Digital cities](#)
[Digital solutions](#)
[Resources](#)
[Newsroom](#)
[Get in touch](#)

THE FIRST DIGITAL SOLUTION

[Back to the top](#)

INTRO

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ABOUT

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SUBTITLE

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GALLERY

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Arctic communication subsidised by

Snapshot 8 - Full website / Resources

Snapshot 9 - Full website / What's news?

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SEND US A MESSAGE

Nom *

Prénom *

E-mail *

Objet *

Message *

[Send my message](#)

* All fields are required.

Snapshot 10 - Full website / Get in touch

Leading urban water management to its digital future

digital-water.city
 digitalwater_eu

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